

1 **Nr5a2 is required for TE lineage commitment.**

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7 Specific usage of nuclear factors during discrete phases of ES cell differentiation during development of
8 pluripotent stem cells to developmental zones and embryonic tissues is not completely understood.
9 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
10 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Nr5a2
11 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells in the trophectoderm of the human embryo.

12 Citations

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1. Festuccia, N., Vandormael-Pournin, S., Chervova, A., Geiselmann, A., Langa-Vives, F., Coux, R.X., Gonzalez, I., Collet, G.G., Cohen-Tannoudji, M. and Navarro, P., 2024. Nr5a2 is dispensable for zygotic genome activation but essential for morula development. Science, 386(6717), p.eadg7325.